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Grant agreement N. 773139

DELIVERABLE N° 6.1

**Title: Project website and
social media accounts**

Validation of diagnostic tests to support plant health

Due date:	Month 3
Actual submission date	13-09-2018
Start date of the project	01-05-2018
Deliverable lead contractor (organization name)	EPPO
Participants (Partners short names)	All partners
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Level of dissemination	Public
Type of Deliverable	Websites, patents filings, etc.

Abstract:

The website constitutes a key communication tool in order to increase the project visibility and to share knowledge and information about the project. It is the most important and immediate point of reference for all target audiences. The website was published at the end of July 2018 (M 3).

The VALITEST website Url is: <https://www.valitest.eu/>

It contains all relevant information about the project (project objectives, information, news, event announcements, public reports and analysis).

The website also hosts a reserved area dedicated to internal communication and a collaborative platform.

The social media buttons (Twitter and Flickr) are inserted to guarantee constant connection with the VALITEST social media account.

The website will be regularly updated and improved with all the news about the project, including its outcomes, events, interviews, official articles and publications.

Screenshots are presented.

Partners involved: EPPO and all partners

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WELCOME TO VALITEST

Welcome to VALITEST

Introduction and context

Global food security is the most significant challenge mankind is facing in the 21st century due to the 'perfect storm' of a growing population (estimated to exceed 9 billion by 2050), climate change, demand for energy, increased pressure on natural resources, slowing of agricultural productivity growth and decline in the land area under agriculture. Additionally, although it is estimated that a 50% increase in food production will be needed by 2050, currently a quarter of the world's crops are lost to pests, causing major economic losses and social impacts globally. Protecting crops against these losses from farm to fork is critical for achieving sustainable and competitive agriculture as well as for the protection of biodiversity and ecosystems. Establishing smart surveillance mechanisms is essential to the fulfilment of this important goal, as these enable effective monitoring and control of introduction and spread of plant pest.

Early diagnosis and a rapid response are crucial to reduce the risk of entry and spread of plant pests and ultimately their impacts. Furthermore, it is recognized that plant pests can be managed most effectively when control measures are implemented at an early stage of infestation. National Plant Protection Organizations (NPPOs) routinely perform pest diagnosis as part of export certification, import inspections, pest surveillance and eradication programs. In 2016, the Commission on Phytosanitary Measures adopted a recommendation on diagnostics recognizing that 'pest diagnosis is a cross-cutting issue that underpins most International Plant Protection

Why companies should be interested?

- VALITEST aims to bring onto the market **tests validated** according to international standards and produced by small and medium size **companies manufacturing diagnostic kits. Even if you are not a partner** there will be opportunities for you to have your kits evaluated during the tests performance studies organized in WP1 ([link](#)).
- VALITEST aims to establish an **EU association of the Plant Health Diagnostic Industry**
- VALITEST aims to develop an **EU Plant Health Diagnostic Charter**.

Read more in [WP7](#), and identify [partners](#)

Work Packages and deliverables

Quick links

[WP 1 : VALIDATION OF TESTS FOR IDENTIFIED NEEDS AND SPECIFIC PESTS](#)

[WP 2 : IMPROVEMENT OF THE VALIDATION PROCESS](#)

[WP 3 : QUALITY ASSURANCE FOR REFERENCE MATERIALS FOR VALIDATION PURPOSES](#)

[WP 4 : ANALYSIS OF DEMAND FOR TESTING AND IMPACTS](#)

[WP 5 : OPTIMISATION OF PROFICIENCY EVALUATION FOR A HORIZONTAL ASSESSMENT](#)

[WP 6 : DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND TRAINING](#)

[WP 7 : MARKET EXPLOITATION OF THE PROJECT RESULTS](#)

[WP 8 : MANAGEMENT OF THE CONSORTIUM AND THE PROJECT](#)

[WP 9 : ETHICS REQUIREMENTS](#)

Work Package 1

[Validation of tests for identified needs and specific pests](#)

WP Leaders : Dr. Marcel Westenberg and Dr Maja Ravnikar

WP1 focus on validation of tests using different methods (i.e. (real-time) PCR, LAMP, ELISA, LFD) according to EPPO Standard PM 7/098, but improved especially by including a statistical approach developed in the frame work of WP2.

Performance criteria of several tests will be determined by organizing interlaboratory test performance studies (TPS) according to EPPO Standard PM 7/122 in which participating laboratories will use the same test for analysing identical sets of reference samples simulating the samples routinely analysed.

Two rounds of tests performance studies will be organised.

- The first round will be organized in early 2019 for six prioritized pests (*Erwinia amylovora*, *Pantoea stewartii*, *citrus tristeza virus*, *plum pox virus*, *Fusarium circinatum* and *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*) in a range of matrices and for a range of methods.
- The second round will be performed in 2020 on pests and associated tests based on the needs of stakeholders and to the market analysed in the framework of WP4.

Erwinia amylovora

Partners

All [Research Institution](#) [SME](#) [Intergovernmental Organisation](#) [Industry](#) [NPPO](#)

Partner's general description and participants

	<p>Agence Nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l'alimentation, de l'environnement et du travail www.anses.fr</p>
<p>ANSES is a public safety agency accountable to the French Ministries of Health, Agriculture, the Environment, Labour and Consumer Affairs. ANSES undertakes monitoring, expert assessment, research and reference activities in a broad range of topics that encompass human health, animal health and well-being, and plant health. It offers a cross-cutting perspective on health issues by assessing health risks and benefits. Its monitoring, vigilance and surveillance work provides input for risk assessment. ANSES is participating in the project through Plant Health Laboratory (LSV), one of its dedicated laboratories.</p> <p>The Plant Health Laboratory is the reference, scientific and technical support body of ANSES for all subjects concerning risks to plant health. LSV has 80 staff members, specialists in diagnostics, experts in bacteriology, virology, mycology, nematology, entomology and invasive plants, especially for quarantine pests. The laboratory covers all fields related to plant health: development and validation of analytical methods, identification of plant pests, expert appraisals on invasive plant species on cultivated land.</p> <p>ANSES is involved in many European, bilateral and multilateral research projects, either as coordinator or as partner</p>	
<p>Role and participation in the project</p> <p>ANSES will coordinate the project and will lead the WPS (Optimization of proficiency evaluation for a horizontal assessment). The LSV will participate in all WPs, except WP7.</p>	

Participants

Géraldine ANTHOINE

Géraldine Anthoine, PhD-engineer is a senior scientist and nematologist. She initially worked on virology. She has a long experience, more than 20 years, in laboratory activities (analysis, evaluation of tests, drafting of operating procedures ...) in the framework of National Reference Laboratory's mandate. She is also involved in standards development at national, regional (EPPC) and international (FAO - IPPC - TRDP) levels.

She also acts as technical assessor for national accreditation bodies.

Géraldine Anthoine speaks fluent French and English.

Géraldine Anthoine is the coordinator of the project.

This page is under construction and will be available soon

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Training & Events

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2018 MAY "Kick-off" meeting EU project Valitest

29 The kickoff meeting of the EU funded H2020 project VALITEST took place at Anses (Maison Alfort, France) on the 31st of May.

2018 No training for the moment

2018 No Proficiency test for the moment

Social media (on 2018-09-06)

The screenshot shows the Twitter profile of the Valitest EU Project (@ValitestProject). The profile picture is a circular logo with the word "Valitest" in green. The header banner features a group photo of project members in front of a wall with the "anses" logo. The profile statistics are: 10 Tweets, 13 Following, 44 Followers, 10 Likes, 0 Lists, and 0 Moments. The bio states: "A multi actor project to generate validation data and improve processes for plant pest diagnostic." It also mentions "Joined May 2018" and "Photos and videos".

Valitest EU Project
@ValitestProject

A multi actor project to generate validation data and improve processes for plant pest diagnostic

Joined May 2018

Photos and videos

Tweets **Tweets & replies** **Media**

Valitest EU Project @ValitestProject · Aug 11
The survey on the first 6 pests selected for the interlaboratory comparisons has been launched. Objective to determine which tests are mainly used in Plant pest diagnostic labs. Other surveys to come! @EPPOnews @Be_Phytopath @Anses_fr @IpadLab_ @LOEWEBiochemica @ClearDetections

Valitest EU Project @ValitestProject · Aug 4
Thanks @neilboonham

Neil Boonham @neilboonham
Diagnostics ideas cafe @icpp2018 collections, protocols, validation and standards - common problems need collaboration to reach common goals across the world

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